

New Dianthraquinones from *Cassia Siamea* Lam. Part I. Structure of Cassianin and Siameanin

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Three dianthraquinone pigments, viz., cassianin, siameanin, and siameadin from *Cassia siamea* Lam. (Fam. Leguminosae, Sub-family, Caesalpinoae) have been isolated. The chemistry of the first two has been discussed.

Dianthraquinones and their further condensation products are of rare occurrence in nature and only two of these, viz., hypericin^{1,2} and dirhein^{3,4}, have been isolated from higher plants, *Hypericum elegans*, Fam. Guttiferac and *Rheum palmatum* L., Fam. Polygonacea, respectively, the others being obtained from fungal and mould metabolites.

Cassia siamea Lam. is a many-branched large tree attaining a height of 15-18 metres and a girth of 2-3 metres. It bears small bright yellow flowers, which appear during April-June and October-December. The hollow space of the wood of this plant is reported to contain a yellow compound, chrysophanhydranthrone⁵, $C_{15}H_{12}O_3$, whereas a toxic alkaloid⁶, $C_{14}H_{19}O_3N$, has been isolated from its pods and leaves.

The cortical region of the trunk bark of *C. siamea* contains reddish brown patches. From air-dried, powdered trunk-bark of this plant three new pigments, viz., cassianin, siameanin, and siameadin, have been isolated besides betulin, betulinic acid, lupeol, and a neutral product, m.p. 168-70°. A method has been developed for their separation and isolation in a pure and homogeneous state. The isolation procedure is described in Chart I.

The homogeneity of cassianin, siameanin, and siameadin has been established by paper chromatography as also by TLC. Cassianin is sparingly soluble in acetone, chloroform, ethyl acetate, ethanol, and benzene; fairly soluble in a mixture of benzene-acetone (1:1) or in benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1); it is freely soluble in dioxane and insoluble in light petroleum. The compound crystallises from benzene and ethyl acetate in orange-red needles, which do not melt but decompose at 350-60°. The composition of cassianin is $C_{30}H_{18}O_9$, as derived from its elemental analysis and from the analysis of its various derivatives as also from the determination of its mass number and from the mass number of its acetate. It is insoluble in 5% aqueous sodium bicarbonate but soluble in 5% aqueous sodium carbonate and sodium hydroxide solution; it reduces neither Tollen's reagent nor Fehling's solution.

1. Brockmann and Sanno, *Naturwiss.*, 1953, 40, 461; Gheorghiu and Ionescu-Matiu, *Chem. Abs.*, 1900, 54, 23184.
2. Brockmann, and Pampus, *Naturwiss.*, 1954, 41, 88.
- 2a. Hörhammer *et al.*, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1959, 292/64, 591.
3. Iwakawa, *Arch. Exp. Path. Pharm.*, 1911, 65, 315.
4. Wells, *Phil. J. Sci.*, 1910, 14, 1.

CHART I

UV and visible spectra of cassianin are typical of polyhydroxyanthraquinones⁵⁻⁷ and run parallel to those of chrysophanol (I) and emodin (II). This view has been substantiated from its reactions with quinonoidal reagents and colour reactions with ethanolic magnesium acetate and other relevant experiments. IR spectrum of cassianin has the peak absorption at 2.94 μ (bonded hydroxyl), 5.95 μ (non-chelated carbonyl), 6.15 μ (chelated carbonyl), and 7.28 μ (β -C.Me). It contains 2-C.Me and five phenolic hydroxyls, which are not vicinal, as the compound fails to react with methylene iodide and also to produce any characteristic colour with zirconium nitrate⁸. It forms a penta-acetyl derivative, m.p. 243-45° and a pentamethyl ether. UV spectrum of penta-acetylcassianin is typical of polyhydroxyanthraquinone acetate. IR spectrum of penta-acetylcassianin shows the peak absorptions for phenolic ester at 5.6 μ , non-chelated carbonyl at 5.98 μ , -C.Me at 7.28 μ , the absorption band for acetate stretching being discernible at 8.3-8.5 μ . Thus out of nine oxygen atoms in cassianin, five occur as phenolic hydroxyls, the remaining four being found to be associated with four quinone carbonyls [which are both chelated (6.15 μ) and non-chelated (5.97 μ) as revealed from a comparison of the IR spectra of cassianin and its acetate]. This has been further corroborated by reductive acetylation of cassianin and other experiments. When refluxed with zinc dust, acetic acid, and acetic anhydride, the compound yields a nona-acetyl derivative, $C_{30}H_{18}(O.COCH_3)_9$, m.p. 173-75°. Regeneration of cassianin by saponification of this acetyl compound and its subsequent aerial oxidation and acidification confirm the presence of a diquinonoid moiety in the compound. Further confirmatory evidence obtained has been discussed in the sequel.

Production of only β -methylanthracone on distillation of cassianin with zinc dust, coupled with the experimental results above, indicates the compound to be a dianthraquinone derivative; both the anthraquinone moieties bear a β -methyl group. Since the compound is soluble in sodium carbonate and insoluble in sodium bicarbonate, only one of the hydroxyls in phenyl nucleus occupies β -position, the rest being attached to α -carbon atoms. Reductive cleavage with alkaline sodium dithionite at 90° made a neat dissection in the molecule of cassianin, giving rise to chrysophanol (I), m.p. 193-94°, and emodin (II), m.p. 254-55°; these two have been identified by the usual procedure and occurrence of which has been frequently observed in Leguminosae and its sub-family, Caesalpinae⁹, to which *Cassia siamea* belongs.

The very isolation of chrysophanol (I) and emodin (II) from reductive cleavage products of cassianin proves that it is a polyhydroxydianthraquinone, formed most plausibly

5. Bowie *et al.*, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1962, 15, 336.
6. "Organic Electronic Spectral Data", Vol. II, p. 432, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1953-55.
7. Birch and Massey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 2215.
8. Cooke & Thomson, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1963, 16, 695.
9. "Biogenesis of Natural Compounds", edited by Marcel Florin & Howard Mason, Academic Press, New York, 1962.

by the oxidative coupling of (I) and (II) through free radical intermediates involving linkage at $\alpha\alpha'$ positions (III). Such a linkage has been observed in all the dianthraquinones known so far. The possibility of the structure (IV) for cassianin is ruled out as it fails to form a hemiacetal. The third alternative (V) for cassianin is not unlikely, but if the biogenesis of hypericin (VI) be acceptable for cassianin, structure (III) would be the most logical formulation for this dianthraquinone compound.

This is the first instance of the occurrence in higher plant of dianthraquinone, retaining all the quinonoid carbonyls, because in hypericin (VI) and dirhein²³ two quinonoid carbonyls are missing.

Siameanin, $C_{30}H_{18}O_8$ (analysis and mass number), the congener of cassianin, decomposes at 323-25° and is sparingly soluble in benzene, ether, chloroform, acetone, and ethanol. It is insoluble in light petroleum and crystallises from benzene-ethyl acetate (2:1) in red micro-needles. It is insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate and sodium carbonate (5%) but soluble in 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. Its colour reactions are practically the same as those of cassianin with quinonoidal reagents and ethanolic magnesium acetate. Light absorption of siameanin in UV and visible regions of the spectrum resembles that of polyhydroxyanthraquinones^{6,8}. I.R. spectrum of the compound

shows absorptions at 3.05μ (bonded hydroxyl), 5.95μ (non-chelated carbonyl), 6.18μ (chelated carbonyl), and 7.28μ (-C.Me).

Siameanin bears four phenolic hydroxyl groups in its molecule and forms a tetra-acetyl derivative, m.p. $170-72^\circ$, and a tetramethyl ether, m.p. 250° , their IR spectra being similar to those of cassianin. Reductive acetylation yields a yellow octa-acetyl compound, $C_{20}H_{14}(O.COMe)_8$, m.p. $162-63^\circ$, which shows the absence of the original quinonoid groups, when tested with the usual reagents. Deacetylation of this octa-acetyl compound, followed by aerial oxidation, regenerated siameanin, like cassianin. It therefore contains four phenolic hydroxyl groups and four quinone carbonyls, indicating the diquinonoid structure for siameanin. When distilled with zinc dust, this compound furnishes only β -methylantracene, whereas reductive fission with alkaline sodium dithionite dissects the molecule just into two halves, fragments of which have been identified as chrysophanol (I). This eventually proves siameanin to be a dianthraquinone originating from two molecules of chrysophanol (I). From the physical and chemical data available so far, the constitution of siameanin is postulated as (VII), based on similar arguments for the structure elucidation of its congener, cassianin.

The nuclear magnetic resonance spectra of cassianin penta-acetate and of siameanin tetra-acetate confirm the structures of the corresponding dianthraquinones.

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